

ANNUAL PLAN

20
25

ABOUT ODISSEI

ODISSEI is the National Research Infrastructure for Social Sciences with diverse components, including access to data, expertise and computing, and offers a wide range of support opportunities. The infrastructure is a collaborative consortium of 45 member organisations, including social sciences faculties in the Netherlands, CBS, public research agencies, and research institutes. Its explicit aim is to unite the social sciences and create a common, national infrastructure for research.

We maintain and develop strategic partnerships with the leading academic and research institutions in the Netherlands, including [CBS](#), [DANS](#), [eScience Center](#), [SURF](#), and [Centerdata](#).

Through these partnerships, we provide access to the ODISSEI core facilities. ODISSEI also collaborates with [CLARIAH](#) (Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) to support various intersecting developments across the Social Science and Humanities domain.

ODISSEI was launched in 2016 and the coordination is hosted by the Erasmus University School of Social and Behavioral Sciences. All ODISSEI member organisations contribute to the operational budget of ODISSEI and ensure its financial sustainability and the continuity of services. Strategic development of new facilities is financed by external grants, especially NWO's Large Scale Research Infrastructure grants. In the past, ODISSEI secured financing of over €25m through Roadmap and SSHOC-NL grants, which were awarded in this scheme.

Internationally, ODISSEI is involved in [ERICs](#) (European Research Infrastructure Consortia), which include [SHARE](#) (the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe) and the [European Social Survey](#). It is the current host of the [IPDLN](#) (the International Population Data Linkage Network, a worldwide network of researchers interested in data linkage).

ODISSEI IN NUMBERS

52,000

Interviews conducted by ODISSEI Surveys

16

Projects using the ODISSEI Secure Super
Computer

84

Summer School alumni

1,334

Publications

2,250,000

Minutes in the LISS panel provided for free
to researchers

1,015

Attendees at events

45

Members

3,028

Searches on the ODISSEI Portal
in the last 12 months

8,550

Datasets in the ODISSEI Portal

623

CBS Microdata Research Projects financed

MESSAGE FROM THE CHAIR

This Annual Plan for 2025 marks a momentous moment in the development of ODISSEI. On December 31st, the ODISSEI Roadmap project will end and ODISSEI will move into a new phase of development with many exciting new opportunities for researchers. Despite an extremely challenging financial environment for the sector, ODISSEI begins this new phase of development in good health. ODISSEI membership in 2025 will continue to provide member organizations with the same services as during the roadmap project. CBS Microdata Grants, LISS Grants, OSSC (ODISSEI Secure Super Computer) access, SoDa (Social Data Analytics) Fellowships, the ODISSEI Summer School, the ODISSEI Conference, and much more will all be continued. These core services will be continuously developed. We have now completed the first year of the SSHOC-NL project in collaboration with CLARIAH and in 2025 these collaborations will start to bear fruit, with greater integration of services such as SANE (Safe Analytical Environment), the ODISSEI Portal, and benchmarking platform.

At the time of writing we are also awaiting confirmation that several PDI-SSH (Platform Digital Infrastructure) projects will receive structural financing and will be incorporated into the ODISSEI Framework. This would mean whole new services being available through ODISSEI including Firmbackbone, which enables secure access to enriched data from the Chamber of Commerce (KvK), PopNet which provides tools for analyzing Population Scale Networks in the CBS Remote Access Environment, D3I which provides researchers with a Data Donation Platform so that they can legally and securely collect and link digital trace data, and PANL which provides a participant platform so that researchers can quickly, easily and cheaply deploy experiments and microtasks at scale. On top of this we were able to secure €2.4 million in co-financing from Member Organizations for the Macroscopic proposal which sets out a bold agenda for integrated Social Science Infrastructure in an age of AI. In 2025 we hope to have this proposal awarded. All these developments taken together mean that 2025 will be an exciting new era for ODISSEI's development where we can begin to enjoy the ever increasing returns on investment in the form of wonderful new research projects.

For me it is also a personal point of change. As of December 31st I will be stepping down as the Chair of the ODISSEI Management Board after almost 10 years. My successor will be Prof Daniel Oberski of Utrecht University who will take on the role of Scientific Director, setting a new and exciting agenda for ODISSEI's development. He will be ably supported by Tom Emery as Executive Director, who remains the head of the Coordination Team at Erasmus. It has been a great privilege to help ODISSEI grow from a loose collection of initiatives in the Social Sciences to a fully fledged national infrastructure consisting of a myriad of services to support ground breaking research. I have immense pride that I leave my position as Chair knowing that ODISSEI is only just beginning and that the most exciting breakthroughs and discoveries are still very much in ODISSEI's future.

PEARL DYKSTRA
CHAIR, ODISSEI

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GOVERNANCE

ODISSEI is the **Dutch National Infrastructure for Social Science** and provides access to a federated set of services to ODISSEI member organizations. Its explicit mission is to provide researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct ground-breaking research and embrace the computational turn in social inquiry.

Through ODISSEI, researchers have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections as well as **innovative and diverse new forms of data**. These can be linked to administrative data at Statistics Netherlands (CBS). Combining data from a wide range of sources enables researchers to answer new, exciting, interdisciplinary research questions and to investigate existing questions in novel, new ways.

ODISSEI now consists of **45 member organizations** who have all signed the participants agreement and committed their financial contribution to ODISSEI. As part of ODISSEI's new plan of work, 35 member organisations have already committed to ODISSEI membership until 2031.

The **Supervisory Board** consists of seven members: Claes de Vreese (DSW, chair), Susan Branje (DSW), Maarten van Ham (DSW), Viola Angelini (DEB), Hanneke Imbens (Statistics Netherlands), Beate Völker (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), and Paulette Flore (public research institutes).

The **Management Board** consists of eleven members: Pearl Dykstra (EUR, Chair), , Daniel Oberski (UU, Chair-elect), Tom Emery (EUR, Exec. Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU), Jessica Piotrowski (UvA), Marcel Das (Centerdata), Ran van den Boom (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Collete Bos (NLeSC), and Anja Smit (DANS). The Management Board meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work. Pearl Dykstra will continue as Chair of the ODISSEI Management Board until the end of 2024, and the ODISSEI Supervisory Board and Management Board has appointed Professor Daniel Oberski as Chair Elect of the Management Board.

The **Coordination Team** is composed of Tom Emery (Exec. Director), Lucas van der Meer (Chief Technical Officer), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Theodora Canciu (Project Manager), Evgeniia Krichever (Communications Manager), Angelica Maineri (Data Manager) and Sofia den Haan (Project Officer).

An **International Advisory Board** has been established, including Julia Lane (New York University), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch (CESSDA), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University).

PROGRAMME OF WORK

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1

DATA FACILITY

1.1

CBS Microdata Access

1.2

ODISSEI Portal

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ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

1.4

Secure Analysis Environment
(SANE)

The Data Facility supports access, linkage, and analysis of sensitive data in a safe, secure, and ethical manner.

1.1. CBS MICRODATA ACCESS

ODISSEI stimulates the use of the rich microdata at Statistics Netherlands (CBS) and supports further development of the remote access environment.

Task leader

Ran van den Boom (r.vandenboom@cbs.nl)

ODISSEI facilitates access to CBS microdata. In 2024 ODISSEI co-financed the development of MUZIEK, a new self-service portal which will allow users to better manage costs and oversee operational projects. ODISSEI is also financing the development of partially automated output checks which will reduce throughput time and costs of these checks.

In 2025 ODISSEI will offer two rounds of grants for free microdata access (MAG) (**€95,000**). The MAG facilitate access to microdata from Statistics Netherlands by offering free of charge access for researchers at ODISSEI member organisations, targeting early career researchers in particular. In total 10-12 projects will be financed. Despite modest grant amounts averaging €7,500, their impact is substantial, enabling projects that are otherwise infeasible and introducing new users to the potential of administrative data.

Moreover, ODISSEI has launched two new initiatives to support users: free authorisations for new microdata users and the ODISSEI storage facility. Any new users of CBS Microdata at ODISSEI Member Organizations can register for free [here](#). This saves €350 each time and supports a new generation of researchers in using administrative data. Projects utilising microdata sometimes result in large files that are of interest to other projects, but a significant fee to store the files limits the reuse potential of them.

Using the ODISSEI Storage Facility, researchers at ODISSEI member organisations can store large files that were created using CBS microdata for free, boosting the reuse of those files. The facility has already received ample interest from researchers working on complex projects and is supporting onward use of many OSSC projects that generate high resolution data high reuse potential.

The metadata of these large files is made findable via the ODISSEI Portal to enhance reuse, and the code written to generate them will be listed in the ODISSEI Code Library to support documentation and transparency.

In the coming period, efforts to support the development of the Remote Access Environment will continue with the launch of MUZIEK, the beta testing of automated output checking, and the launch of a new interface for the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer which will enable researchers to use the supercomputing environment.

These technical investments are gradually **transforming research** within the CBS Remote Access Environment and in 2025 a further **€296,000** will be invested in hardware and software upgrades. Together with the investments in access, this means that the total budget for CBS Microdata Access is **€391,000**.

Research Results

Educational attainment and psychiatric diagnoses: a national registry data and two-sample Mendelian randomization study

In this study, the authors investigated the causal relationship between educational attainment and mental health conditions using two research designs. They first compared the relationship between EA and 18 psychiatric diagnoses within-sibship in Dutch national registry data (N = 1.7 million), thereby controlling for unmeasured familial factors. Second, they applied two-sample Mendelian randomization, which uses genetic variants related to educational attainment or psychiatric diagnosis as instrumental variables, to test whether there is a causal relation in either direction. The results suggested that lower educational attainment causally increases the risk of major depressive disorder, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, alcohol dependence, generalized anxiety disorder and post-traumatic stress disorder diagnoses. The authors found evidence of a causal effect of attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder on educational attainment. For schizophrenia, anorexia nervosa, obsessive-compulsive disorder and bipolar disorder, the results were inconsistent across the different approaches, highlighting the importance of using multiple research designs and diverse linked data via CBS to understand complex relationships, such as between education and mental health conditions.

Demange, P.A., Boomsma, D.I., van Bergen, E. et al. Educational attainment and psychiatric diagnoses: a national registry data and two-sample Mendelian randomisation study. *Nat. Mental Health* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44220-024-00245-x>

Figure 1: Phenotypic and genetic correlations between diagnoses.

1.2. ODISSEI PORTAL

The ODISSEI Portal combines metadata from various repositories into one interface, allows semantic queries to support findability, and facilitates data access.

Task leader

Jacco van Ossenbruggen (j.r.van.Ossenbruggen@vu.nl)

The **ODISSEI Portal** is a gateway to important data collections in the Dutch Social Sciences. It promotes the reuse and linking of existing datasets, which can result in reducing research costs, achieving better data quality, and leading to answering new, groundbreaking research questions.

The ODISSEI Portal includes rich metadata from over 8,000 datasets from social science data collections held at CBS, LISS Data Archive, IISG, DataverseNL, and DANS Data Station SSH. The metadata is enriched using multilingual vocabularies to improve the search experience, and can be exported in various machine-readable formats to support reuse.

The latest format addition, the Croissant format, allows using the metadata for advanced machine learning applications. To encourage the innovative combination of data sources, linkage opportunities are included as part of the metadata: this allows promoting the linkage between the data in the LISS data archive with CBS microdata.

The Portal is live and being continuously developed with updates on a quarterly basis. In 2025, the functionality of the Portal will be further extended through the piloting of the Data Access Broker, which provides easier access to the underlying data by processing licences and data access requirements and automating elements of the data access process.

The Portal is freely accessible and in 2024 there were over 3,000 searches, with a noticeable upward trend since the first version of the Portal was launched. The Portal working group consists of representatives from DANS, VU, SURF, and the ODISSEI Coordination Team. To further assist researchers in reusing data, ODISSEI with the PDI-SSH FAIR Expertise Hub has also built a [code library](#), collecting analytical scripts used to pre-process and analyse CBS microdata and LISS panel data.

In 2025, the Portal will be further developed within the SSHOC-NL project, with a focus on:

- improving the way access conditions and licences for reuse are standardised and displayed,
- including metadata from additional providers, including the **Consortium Individual Development (CID)**, **FirmBackBone**, and metadata from the CBS user-generated datasets available in the ODISSEI data storage facility at CBS,
- improving international reach by having the ODISSEI Portal harvested by the **CESSDA Data Catalogue**, and
- improving alignment with **CLARIAH** and their portal Ineo.

The budget for this work in 2025 is **€465,000** and consists of engineers, developers, and data stewards who develop, deploy and populate the portal.

ODISSEI Code Library

ODISSEI FAIR support team

Erasmus University Rotterdam - ODISSEI ·
fairsupport@odissei-data.nl

Welcome

The ODISSEI code library contains a collection of scripts detailing data processing and analysis steps of projects using LISS panel data and CBS (Statistics Netherlands) microdata. Some of the projects receive funding via [ODISSEI](#).

If you have comments, reach out to the [ODISSEI FAIR support team](#).

Do you want to submit your own project and code to be added to the library?

Please submit an issue using the Submission code issue template on the [GitHub repository](#) or send an email to the [ODISSEI FAIR support team](#).

[CBS microdata](#) [LISS panel](#)

50 entries per page

#	Title	Project lead	Code Language	Public
1	Enhancing Accuracy in Country-Wide Agent-Based Epidemiological Modeling through the Application of 17 Million Individual-Level Microdata Points	Ahmad Hesam		doi
2	Sex and gender differences in primary care help-seeking for common somatic symptoms: a longitudinal study	Aranka van Ballerijng	SPSS	doi
3	Children's strains, parents' pains? How adult	Damiano Uccheddu	Stata	doi

ODISSEI Portal Discover Social Science Datasets Across The Netherlands

Welcome to the prototype of the ODISSEI portal. The ODISSEI Portal combines metadata from a wide variety of research data repositories into a single interface, allowing for advanced semantic queries to support findability, and facilitate data access. The portal is under active development and features and content will be improved throughout the ODISSEI Roadmap project.

This version features a link to the Data Access Broker (DAB) through which open datasets can be downloaded directly. For restricted access datasets, the DAB links to the provider's page for more information. The link to the DAB is listed under Terms > Data Access Place for each dataset.

1 to 10 of 8,569 Results

- Do My Reactions Outweigh My Actions? The Relation between Reactive and Proactive Aggression with Peer Acceptance in Preschoolers**
 Sep 9, 2024 - Leiden University
 da Silva, Brenda M.S.; Weiga, Guida; Rieffe, Carolien; Endedijk, Hinke; Güroğlu, Berna, 2024, "Do My Reactions Outweigh My Actions? The Relation between Reactive and Proactive Aggression with Peer Acceptance in Preschoolers", <https://doi.org/10.34894/PGRG2Q>, ODISSEI Portal, V1
 Data and materials supporting the paper "Do My Reactions Outweigh My Actions? The Relation between Reactive and Proactive Aggression with Peer Acceptance in Preschoolers".
- Persoonlijkheidswaarneming in het selectie-interview**
 Sep 5, 2024 - Utrecht University
 Dam, K. van, 2024, "Persoonlijkheidswaarneming in het selectie-interview", <https://doi.org/10.34894/04IWSJ>, ODISSEI Portal, V1
 Artikel Gedrag & Organisatie. Gedrag & Organisatie, Tijdschrift voor Sociale, Arbeids- & Organisationspsychologie, is een wetenschappelijk tijdschrift voor de Nederlandse en Vlaamse markt. Naast wetenschappelijk onderzoek (gebaseerd op kwantitatief en kwalitatief onderzoek) publice...
- Persoon - klimaat - congruentie van nieuwkomers in de organisatie**
 Sep 5, 2024 - Utrecht University
 Vianen, A.E.M. van; Bruggencate, M. ten, 2024, "Persoon - klimaat - congruentie van nieuwkomers in de organisatie", <https://doi.org/10.34894/097HT6>, ODISSEI Portal, V1
 Artikel Gedrag & Organisatie. Gedrag & Organisatie, Tijdschrift voor Sociale, Arbeids- & Organisationspsychologie, is een wetenschappelijk tijdschrift voor de Nederlandse en Vlaamse markt. Naast wetenschappelijk onderzoek (gebaseerd op kwantitatief en kwalitatief onderzoek) publice...
- Organisatieverandering, strategie en beloning**
 Sep 5, 2024 - Utrecht University
 Vnke, R.H.W., 2024, "Organisatieverandering, strategie en beloning", <https://doi.org/10.34894/0M0FBK>, ODISSEI Portal, V1
 Artikel Gedrag & Organisatie. Gedrag & Organisatie, Tijdschrift voor Sociale, Arbeids- & Organisationspsychologie, is een

1.3. ODISSEI SECURE SUPERCOMPUTER

The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) enables the analysis of highly sensitive data in a highly secure HPC environment.

Task leader

Michel Scheerman (michel.scheerman@surf.nl)

The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer provides the fastest computing capacity in the Netherlands via the national supercomputer Snellius and consists of an enclave of Statistics Netherlands (CBS) within the domain of SURF. This virtual IT environment offers a high performance computing environment that meets the requirements of Statistics Netherlands in legal, technical and security requirements.

The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer is available for use by all researchers working at a SURF member organisation. SURF is constantly working on improving the user experience and maintaining the strictest security levels of the facility. Use of the OSSC has been increasingly rapidly. Through 2024, fourteen projects were supported in implementing and using the OSSC, including the training of large language models on microdata for improved socio-economic modelling.

Earlier this year, ODISSEI, in collaboration with SURF and CBS, organised workshops on Cluster Computing for Social Scientists to familiarize the researchers with the facility. These workshops sold out very rapidly. In response to the high demand, the teams will organise further workshops through 2025.

The OSSC technical team has been working on improving user-friendliness by implementing the OSSC App Dashboard, which facilitates a Graphical User Interface (GUI) for several apps such as Rstudio and Jupyter Notebooks.

This significantly lowers the barrier for using the OSSC, especially for novice users and those without advanced technical expertise. The OSSC App Dashboard will also simplify planning computing jobs. the dashboard will be in production by late 2024.

The OSSC Trusted Upload and Linkage Procedure (TULP) is designed to safeguard the upload and linkage of large datasets with CBS. This is open for wider use in 2025 and is specifically valuable for linkage of CBS Microdata with large biomedical collections. SURF is also developing an automatic reservation system to improve user friendliness.

OSSC operation in 2025 will cost **€220,000** and is conducted by SURF. These costs provide for the continued operation of the OSSC and integration of these continued developments. The OSSC requires a manual operation in order to comply with the strict protocol and this makes operation expensive. SURF is working closely with the ODISSEI Coordination Team to reduce these long term operational costs of the OSSC.

Future funding applications are being developed to generalize the OSSC protocols as there is significant interest in the system from other domains such as the health and life sciences. If the system can be made part of SURF's general services, it will significantly reduce the operational costs of the OSSC in the long run.

In our project, we estimate the causal effect of daycare on children's mental health and schooling outcomes in the Netherlands, applying complex simulations. At the CBS server, we could only perform the simulation for a small subsample. The OSSC allows us to conduct the simulation for the entire sample within a reasonable period.

Bettina Siflinger, Tilburg University

1.4. SECURE ANALYSIS ENVIRONMENT (SANE)

The Secure analysis environment (SANE) is a virtual container that enables the analysis of sensitive data while ensuring its safety.

Task leader

Lucas van der Meer (lucas@odissei-data.nl)

SANE is a virtual, fully shielded off-the-shelf computing environment containing pre-approved analysis software, such as R and Jupyter notebooks, and access to sensitive data. It allows data providers to maintain complete control while allowing the researcher to study the data conveniently. SANE was developed via a PDI-SSH financed project which entails a collaboration between ODISSEI and CLARIAH, and is executed by SURF.

SANE follows the Five Safes principles and makes use of ISO 270001 certified SURF services. As SANE has a cloud-based infrastructure, it scales almost infinitely. The secure environment has undergone thorough penetration tests to guarantee data providers a high level of safety.

SANE is available on SURF Research Cloud and uses SRAM to form collaborations between data providers and researchers.. Currently 5 research projects are running, in a collaborative effort between data providers and researchers with many more planned for 2025. Interest in using the facility is considerable among the data providers and researchers alike.

SANE is working with data providers including KvK, ING, the Koninklijke Bibliotheek, and Beeld en Geluid to make secure datasets more easily available for researcher purposes and expanding the range of data the researchers have access to.

In the upcoming period, the team will constantly improve and scale-up the production environment and determine the legal framework to use the facility, including for international collaborations. One improvement is the incorporation of a Data Access Broker, which facilitates a seamless and automated access process from data catalogues such as the ODISSEI Portal. SANE aligns with major European initiatives, such as the Data Spaces/EHDS (including the Dutch node of HDAB-NL), EOSC-ENTRUST (alignment with the SATRE specification for TREs), and the Data Governance and Data Acts.

As part of SSHOC-NL, SANE is being intergrated into existing distributed generic infrastructure components and services that are already being used in the SSH ecosystem or national E-infrastructures such as SURF and DANS. This ensures that researchers can access easy-to-use sVREs (secure Virtual Research Environments) suitable for addressing a wide range of practical use cases.

The allocated budget for developments on SANE in 2025 is **€422,000**. This includes €150,000 for developers at SURF to improve the environments workflow, €107,000 for overall technical coordination via EUR, and €165,000 for data integration support across diverse data providers. It is expected that in 2025, SANE will receive structural funding via the PDI-SSH structural funds.

SANE is enabling us to take restricted data from the Dutch Chamber of Commerce (KvK) that has never been available at scale to researchers before and make it securely accessible via a flexible and powerful compute environment. It's an easy to use and simple solution to a common problem in social research.

Wolter Hassink, Co-PI Firmbackbone,
Utrecht University

2

OBSERVATORY

2.1

Data Collection Committee

2.2

LISS panel

2.3

Media Content Analysis Lab

The Observatory sustains and optimises valuable, long-standing data collections and collection and integration of new types of data.

2.1. DATA COLLECTION COMMITTEE

The Data Collection Committee finances critical large-scale data collections, ensures they have a sustainable future, and integrates them into a diverse data landscape.

Task leader

Marika Knoef (M.G.Knoef@tilburguniversity.edu)

ODISSEI ensures Dutch participation in cross-national data collections, identifies gaps, and allocates resources for longitudinal data collections. The Committee has facilitated the transition of data collections to sustainable models and provides greater financial stability to critical long term collections.

Four members of the ODISSEI Data Collection Committee have been appointed: Marika Knoef (Chair), Gerbert Kraaykamp, Peter Lugtig, and Janine van der Maat. ODISSEI finances Dutch participation in European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERIC) and surveys of key strategic importance. Currently ODISSEI is committed to supporting the **European Social Survey (ESS)**, the **Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)**, **Nederland Kiezersonderzoek (NKO)**, the **Generations and Gender Programme (GGP)**, **International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)**, the **European Value Study (EVS)**, and the **Luxembourg Income Study (LIS)**.

The data collected via ODISSEI are fed into international collaborations that support hundreds of thousands of researchers across the globe. It is vital that the Dutch population is represented in these collections to ensure that the analysis of researchers worldwide can be understood in relation to the Netherlands. These collections are also extensively used by the Dutch Research Community including economists, political scientists, sociologists, and psychologists with ODISSEI's commitment ensuring that they remain free at the point of use.

In 2024 NWO agreed to provide financial support to the data collection costs of Survey ERIC's. This commitment will support ODISSEI investments in ensuring that these surveys transition to more sustainable modes of data collection. Together with the investments made via SSHOC-NL means that data collection costs for existing rounds of data collection are secure.

In 2025, ODISSEI will continue the financing the Country Team Operator of SHARE at Utrecht University under Bella Struminskaya (€45,000), and the National Coordinator of ESS at Tilburg University under Tim Reeskens (€55,000). ODISSEI will also continue the membership of the Luxembourg Income Study (€30,000) and field the 2025 round of the International Social Survey Programme (€30,000).

Finally, as part of SSHOC-NL the digitalization of the Centraal Bureau of Genealogies records will be undertaken, costing €114,000 and enabling the linkage and analysis of large scale genealogical records for socio-economic research. This work is being conducted by the International Institute for Social History (ISSG) in Amsterdam.

These activities taken together amount to **€274,000** in investments in the year 2025 and will ensure that Dutch Researchers continue to have access to an eclectic and high quality range of internationally and historically comparable data sources.

2.2. LISS PANEL

LISS is an online panel that provides researchers with the opportunity to field questionnaires, run experiments and collect high-quality research data in a cost-efficient way.

Task leader

Marcel Das (marcel.das@centerdata.nl)

The panel, which is run by Centerdata and financed by ODISSEI, consists of some 7,500 individuals from approximately 5,000 households and is a representative sample of the adult population in the Netherlands. ODISSEI finances the maintenance of the panel. ODISSEI Member Organizations receive a discount of 20% when fielding general studies in the LISS panel and this amounted to €152,636 in discounts for member organizations in 2023.

ODISSEI also supports researchers through open calls, which offer free panel time. Successful projects cover a wide array of topics that are relevant nowadays, such as unequal exposure to heat and self-presentation strategies in a context of AI-based recruitment. They are showcased on the ODISSEI website and generate considerable press attention. The seventh round of the LISS panel Grant closed in September 2024, and the award decision will be announced by mid-December. The projects will commence from February 2025. In 2025 a further round of grants will be issued amounting to €95,000.

The LISS panel data itself is very widely used with 36,813 downloads by 8,911 registered users over the last 12 months. LISS panel data was used in 184 publications last year alone. The LISS panel also supports the data collection for other major studies including Nederlands Kiezersonderzoek (NKO), the International Social Survey Panel (ISSP), and the European Value Survey (EVS). The LISS panel is therefore a centerpiece of the Dutch data landscape.

Data from the LISS panel was used for the Predicting Fertility (PreFer) data challenge (see also 3.3 Benchmarking). Over 30 interdisciplinary teams from various countries applied machine learning techniques to the full set of LISS panel core studies to predict who will have a child in the short-term future in the Netherlands.

Moreover, in collaboration with the FAIR Expertise Hub, a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) has been created for the LISS Data Archive, showing a good level of FAIR maturity but also highlighting gaps to be filled in the future and which will be addressed by work elsewhere in SSHOC-NL.

ODISSEI will also provide a €250,000 subsidy to the LISS panel for its core operations and maintenance. This budget will be used for the maintenance of the LISS panel in 2025. Together with the access grants, this means that the total budget for LISS in ODISSEI in 2025 is **€345,000**.

The LISS panel's position as a global leader in innovative data collection will be further strengthened by the integration of tools to execute simultaneous mass online experiments or data collection through data donation by the panel members. The pilots for those initiatives are already ongoing and will continue in the context of the SSHOC-NL project.

LISS panel Project

Filling the EU information deficit mitigates negative EU attitudes among the least knowledgeable. Evidence from a population-based survey experiment.

The cognitive mobilisation thesis suggests that increasing knowledge on the European Union (EU) would lead to increased support for the institution. We test this with a strategic case whereby we provide information on the EU's subsidiarity principle to the citizenry of a small member state and examine whether it mitigates negative EU attitudes. In an original, pre-registered, population-based survey experiment conducted with members of a panel representative of the Dutch population, respondents were assigned randomly to a control group or a treatment: a professionally produced information video mimicking EU communications. Along with estimating the overall treatment effects, based on extant literature we assess whether these effects are moderated by the respondents' prior EU knowledge and level of populist attitudes. Consistent with the information deficit theory, we find that information provision decreases negative attitudes among the least knowledgeable.

(ODISSEI LISS panel grant 2021), van den Hoogen, E., de Koster, W., & van der Waal, J. (2024). Filling the EU information deficit mitigates negative EU attitudes among the least knowledgeable. Evidence from a population-based survey experiment. Journal of European Integration, 46(6), 923–942. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2024.2352765>

2.3. MEDIA CONTENT ANALYSIS LAB

The ODISSEI Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) integrates media content data and software into the wider ODISSEI ecosystem and supports collaborative reuse

Task leader

Rens Vliegthart (rens.vliegthart@wur.nl)

MCAL tackles the major challenge of digital text analysis whereby copyright and GDPR restrictions make it very hard to share media content data by providing a workbench for researchers where they can share data and analyses with strict rights management without the need to read or export the data themselves.

Currently, several Dutch initiatives exist that facilitate retrieval, storage, and analysis of media content (i.e. the infrastructure for content analysis [INCA] at the University of Amsterdam (Trilling et al., 2018), and the Amsterdam Content Analysis Toolkit [AMCaT] at VU Amsterdam (Van Atteveldt et al., 2014). Their use, however, requires considerable programming skills and is currently tailored to a limited set of applications.

As part of the ODISSEI Roadmap Project, the design and architecture of the Media Content Analysis Lab was developed and the data sources and software used in communication sciences was mapped. The MCAL team has created an inventory of publications dealing with the analysis of media content in the Netherlands, the MCALentory.

Almost 200 research papers from the top 30 communication science journals have been selected and manually annotated to extract several features, such as the type of research question, the type of content analysis conducted, the reporting of reliability and quality of the content analysis, and the availability of corpora, datasets, and code and software.

Through collaboration with the FAIR Expertise Hub, VU Amsterdam and **Triply**, the **MCAL inventory** has been transformed into Linked data and enriched. The user-friendly interface provided by the Triply platform allows users to generate insights on the media content analysis field using the format of “data stories”, i.e. a way for users to combine text and interactive data visualisations.

The inventory formed the basis of the Macroscopic proposal which was submitted in Autumn 2024. If awarded, a further €3 million would be invested in constructing the Netherlands Media Corpus in collaboration with CLARIAH and under the joint direction of Theo Araujo & Jessica Piotrowski at University of Amsterdam and Sophie Ham at the Koninklijke Bibliotheek.

The Netherlands Media Corpus would bring together a wide range of web data collections such as those generated by **CAT4SMR** with large scale corpora found at KB and Beeld en Geluid. The integrated framework offered by the Netherlands Media Corpus is vital for secure and distributed training of Large Language Models on restricted Dutch Language media data.

In 2025, whilst the outcome of the Macroscopic proposal is awaited, the MCAL task is on hiatus and is therefore not included in budget for the forthcoming year.

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Created on Feb 22nd, 2023

ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) is the national research infrastructure for the social sciences in the Netherlands. ODISSEI brings together researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct ground-breaking research and embrace the computational turn in social enquiry. More information on <https://odissei-data.nl/en/>

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Introduction to MCAL

Author: Annelien Van Remoortere 0000-0003-1610-2661

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Media Content Analysis Lab: The story hidden in the data

The ODISSEI Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) offers systematic analysis of large corpora of digital media content. The Media Content Analysis Lab seeks to tackle the major challenge of digital text analysis whereby copyright and GDPR restrictions make it very hard to share media content data. In this document, we provide some overview of what is in

[Read the full story](#)

mcal

7,510 statements

Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL)

One of the aims of the Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) is to provide an overview of the field of content analysis research. To this end, the **MCALentory** consists of an inventory of content analytical studies in The Netherlands, 2000-2023. This inventory serves multiple purposes. First, it can be used as a source of inspiration for designing future content analytical studies, for example in terms operationalization of key concepts. Second, the archive can be used for replication studies and meta analyses. Third, data can potentially be used as training data for machine learning algorithms.

3

LABORATORY

3.1

Port

3.2

Mass Online Experiments

3.3

POPNET

The Laboratory opens up new avenues of scientific inquiry by exploiting innovative digital technologies.

3.1. PORT

Port is software that enables individuals to donate their digital trace data to academic research.

Task leader

Laura Boeschoten (L.boeschoten@uu.nl)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) grants all persons within the EU the right to an electronic copy of their personal data (e.g., WhatsApp messages or bank statements), in a so-called 'Data Download Package' (DDP). Citizens can, therefore, now consent to donate relevant information derived from their digital traces to trusted researchers, in a manner that is legally mandatory for data processing companies.

The Port software developed by Utrecht University in conjunction with Eyra, allows researchers to securely analyse DDP data. First, the citizen requests their DDP and uses the Port webtool that is created specifically for each conducted study. This tool extracts only data that is important for the study from the donated file, thereby adhering to GDPR data minimisation instructions. For instance, the citizen's IP address will be removed. This extracting happens locally at the citizen's device, so before actually sharing the data. The citizen is able to inspect and, if it wishes so, amend the data before consenting to share it with us.

Researchers can make use of the Port software in two ways. One version can be used on SURF Research Cloud where researchers can request access using a SURF e-Infra grant, and contact the Port Research Engineer for access on SURF Research Cloud. No direct costs are involved for the researcher, and for many research institutions in the Netherlands, usage agreements are already in place with SURF. Alternatively, Eyra offers usage of Port as a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS).

This does not require any installation or responsibilities for the researcher. However, it does need to be paid by researchers themselves.

Port is 22 projects have conducted with six more studies planned data collection in 2025. In 2025, the software will be extended further. Port will be made interoperable with other secure environments such as SANE and the ODISEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC), requiring the implementation of the controlled vocabularies on data security and data access, and integration with SURF Research Drive, SURF Research Cloud and SURF Authentication and Authorisation services. Port will then be upgraded to allow for more computationally intensive procedures.

The ease of access for both donors and researchers will also be improved, and it will be extended for use in exploratory analysis, in combination with vaults and extensive de-identification procedures. Port will also be further integrated with LISS and other data collections so that participants can be recruited through these studies, and these participants can also donate their data. This work will be led by Utrecht University and is financed by the SSHOC-NL grant. The total budget for this task in 2024 will be **€191,000**. This includes software development (€80,000), Coordination (€17,000), Engineering (€84,000), and use case implementation (€10,000). If structural financing for PDI-SSH is secured, this will also be used to further develop Port.

Figure 3: Port Software: Step-by-step illustration of the workflow that allows for a privacy-preserving analysis of data download package

3.2. MASS ONLINE EXPERIMENTS

The Mass Online Experiments Lab facilitates experiments in which large numbers of participants simultaneously interact in online games under controlled conditions.

Task leader

Rense Corten (r.corten@uu.nl)

Population-level experiments cannot be conducted in the traditional laboratory as they require scale in which network structures are systematically varied across multiple, large-sized, experimental populations.

The Mass Online Experiment Lab overcomes the significant infrastructural and logistic challenges associated with the simultaneous networked participation of many participants and removes barriers-to-entry by providing methodological and organisational research facilities to interested but otherwise ill-equipped domain experts through a series of open calls.

In 2020-2021, the Lab was piloted in an experiment on political polarisation with a further use case to extend the functionality in early 2022. The pilot experiments were built in the **Elixir** programming language, with over 2,000 participants each.

In 2024, the **OBELISS project** developed software that facilitates the execution of behavioural experiments within the LISS panel and using the oTree platform. These two initiatives are stepping stones towards the maturation of a permanent suite of tools for deploying Mass Online Experiments and eliminating the fixed costs associated with such experiments for Dutch researchers. The ability to field such experiments via LISS ensures that participants are selected from a probability based sample and a vast range of background variables can be incorporated into the experimental design.

In the upcoming period, the team will evaluate different types of software that can be used and design a use case that will result in a list of requirements for the general experimental infrastructure to be developed. This use case will then be fielded in the summer of 2025 and used to evaluate the ease of use and scalability of the infrastructure.

A well documented code library will be made available for existing software and well established experimental designs alongside the use case in 2025. In Spring 2025 the team will also establish an implementation of the widely used OTree software on SURF Research Cloud. This will allow Mass Online Experiments to be run in conjunction with the SANE ecosystem. By the end of 2025, these developments will inform an assessment of the labs future operational model and subsequent scalability and usability.

This work will cost **€170,000** in 2025. €100,000 will be spent on coordination and development at Utrecht University to design and deploy the use case experiments. A further €40,000 will be used for incentives in the experiments and €30,000 for the coding and deployment of the experiments and SURF Research Cloud deployment.

This work is exclusively funded by SSHOC-NL and by the end of the project, the Lab will be operational and interoperable with the wider ODISSEI ecosystem including SANE, LISS, and SoDA.

Research Results

Realtime user ratings as a strategy for combatting misinformation: an experimental study. Jonas Stein et al., Utrecht University

Because fact-checking takes time, verdicts are usually reached after a message has gone viral. To study this phenomenon researchers designed an online mass experiment that enabled recipients of an online message to attach veracity assessments. In well-mixed communities, the public display of earlier veracity ratings indeed enhances the correct classification of true and false messages by subsequent users, but crowd intelligence backfires when false information is sequentially rated in ideologically segregated communities, suggesting that network segregation poses an important problem for community misinformation detection.

Stein, J., et al. (2023). Realtime user ratings as a strategy for combatting misinformation: an experimental study. *Nature Scientific Reports*. doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-28597-x

Study setup: Subjects were randomly assigned to ideologically segregated, ideologically integrated, or independent groups and instructed to rate 20 informational messages as true or false. Subjects rated messages sequentially. In segregated and integrated groups, subjects were presented a count of previous group members' rating decisions. Subjects in independent groups made rating decisions without being exposed to previous subjects' decisions. Red (blue) icons represent self-identified conservatives (liberals). The example message in the figure is false and has a conservative leaning. For each rating group, we measured how many correct and incorrect rating decisions were made (right side of the figure, data taken from exemplary groups observed in the experiment). We collected data from 80 rating groups with 50 subjects each, amounting to a total of 80,000 rating decisions.

3.3. POPNET

POPNET supports analysis of longitudinal network data on the entire population of the Netherlands and helps understand the disclosure risks inherent in such complex data.

Task leader

Frank Takes (takes@liacs.nl)

POPNET is a novel digital infrastructure and research community that aims to make longitudinal social network data on the entire population of the Netherlands securely accessible for academic research purposes. It enables new exciting research in an anonymized as well as ethically and legally responsible manner. This research can lead to actionable insights into key issues including segregation, substantive social change, and UN sustainable development goals such as reducing inequality.

As part of SSHOC-NL, POPNET is investing in evaluating disclosure risks in population scale networks and their associated structures. With an increased reliance on non-research data for scientific research, it becomes increasingly difficult to balance data access and data protection, both from a legal and ethical perspective.

The most advanced current use case of data disclosure risk assessment is the analysis of network data extracted from CBS administrative records. This is because the data is highly sensitive, but also exceptionally complex and intensively linked, making disclosure risks particularly hard to assess with conventional approaches common in the areas of statistical disclosure control.

Most applications of such data don't require individual level data, what is of interest is the broader population structure. However, it can be very difficult to determine when the risk of disclosing someones identity from the data has been adequately removed.

POPNET has broken new ground in devising disclosure risk assessment methods that ensure a low risk of data disclosure whilst preserving the high scientific value of the data. An initial version of the POPNET tool has been developed to assess the disclosure risks within a specific dataset rapidly and at scale. In 2025 this will be made available via an initial version of the POPNET platform.

POPNET collaborates intensively with CBS to assess the data disclosure risk at multiple points in the data lifecycle and ensures that these risks are managed and minimised, whilst still providing scientists with the ability to analyse the data through a flexible and user-friendly interface. In SSHOC-NL, the POPNET tool will be made interoperable with a wider range of Social Science and Humanities data, including social media network data and development of methods to increase the interoperability of historical records.

The total budget for this task in 2025 will be **€232,526**. This includes €50,000 for the support of CBS in the development of POPNET and €182,526 for developers in Amsterdam and Leiden. The work will be led by Eelke Heemskerk (University of Amsterdam) and Frank Takes (Leiden University) and is financed by the SSHOC-NL grant. POPNET is also a PDI-SSH project that is awaiting confirmation of structural financing. If awarded, this would enable sustained development of the infrastructure and services as well as alignment with the wider infrastructure landscape.

POPNET

4

HUB

4.1

Coordination

4.2

Education

4.3

Support

The Hub creates a community of infrastructure users and offers the researchers the necessary support for complex and comprehensive modelling of social phenomena.

4.1. COORDINATION

The Coordination Team that is based at EUR is responsible for communicating the full potential of ODISSEI facilities to the research community and engaging ODISSEI partners.

Task leader

Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

ODISSEI, with its growing network of 45 member organizations, continuously attracts new members and expands its reach. The ODISSEI Coordination Team at EUR plays a pivotal role in connecting with potential users, helping them discover the full potential of the research infrastructure. The Coordination Team follows a structured approach: **inform**, **involve**, and **engage**. These three pillars guide the team's efforts in building awareness, encouraging participation, and fostering ongoing involvement.

Through **informing** potential users, the team ensures that researchers across disciplines understand what ODISSEI offers. This outreach is accomplished through regular updates in a newsletter, a new website, a podcast series, and frequent posts on LinkedIn, Bluesky, and X (formerly Twitter). The team's goal here is to clearly communicate the range of research supported by ODISSEI and to showcase the infrastructure's capabilities.

Once researchers are informed, the next step is to **involve** them by inviting active participation in ODISSEI's facilities and events. Key activities include the Annual ODISSEI Conference, Task Insights meetings, thematic meetings, a Summer School, and a dynamic Slack community.

Through these engagements, researchers can experience the infrastructure firsthand, explore its resources, and build collaborative relationships within the community.

For those already using the infrastructure, the team works to **engage** them on a deeper level, fostering sustained and meaningful interaction with the ODISSEI community. Initiatives such as grant information workshops, introductory presentations, and partner events encourage users to remain active participants, continually discovering new ways to benefit from and contribute to ODISSEI.

Beyond community outreach, the Coordination Team also provides essential support to ODISSEI's Supervisory Board, Management Board, and task leaders, handling secretarial and logistical needs to streamline operations. It is the financial controller and reporting body to NWO and other funders. The Coordination Team leads the SSHOC-NL Project, as well as leading ODISSEI grant writing initiatives.

The 2025 budget for Coordination is **€426,000** but this is inclusive of €185,000 which supports CLARIAH coordination as part of SSHOC-NL. ODISSEI Coordination will therefore cost €241,000. It includes 2.5 FTE in the ODISSEI Coordination Team, €50,000 for all events (including the Community Conference), Management, and €30,000 for materials, travel, and training.

4.2. EDUCATION

ODISSEI and its member organisations collaborate in the educational programme to enhance training and skills acquisition in the Dutch Computational Social Sciences domain.

Task leader

Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

In 2024, ODISSEI organised its third ODISSEI Summer School in Computational Social Science in collaboration with SICSS. This immersive summer school provided 21 participants with two full weeks of intensive, high-level training essential to fully leverage the complex elements of the ODISSEI infrastructure. It included specialized modules on network analysis, machine learning, benchmarking approaches, usage of the OSSC, and ethical considerations related to big data. The workshops were delivered by experts from the Social Data Science (SoDa) team, the Benchmarking team, the eScience Center, SURF consultants, and the Coordination Team. The summer school is accredited with ECTS points for graduate students.

The summer school complements a broader programme of workshops specifically geared towards using particular ODISSEI facilities, such as the Microdata Access Grant, the LISS panel Grant, and the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer. These workshops aim to showcase available ODISSEI facilities and significantly lower the threshold for submitting a project proposal. The programme is developed in close collaboration with and executed by, or together with, several key ODISSEI partners: DANS, CBS, Centerdata, Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC), and SURF. In 2025, the educational team will conduct numerous workshops focused on the ODISSEI infrastructure, including workshops on Supercomputing for social scientists with R and Efficient and reproducible research with CBS microdata.

ODISSEI is also organising the Next-Generation Researchers workshop, a hands-on event dedicated to supporting early-career researchers interested in receiving targeted methodological feedback on their ongoing work and learning how to use ODISSEI facilities more efficiently. This workshop primarily targets projects in the social sciences that involve data science, data-related, or methodological challenges. During the workshop, participants will collaborate with the SoDa and eScience teams to address these challenges through interactive, practical sessions. Topics include developing high-quality data analysis pipelines, accessing specialized datasets, conducting causal analyses with simulation-based robustness checks, and performing advanced geospatial, network, or agent-based analyses to enhance research quality.

In 2025, another summer school utilizing ODISSEI facilities is planned, with a new thematic focus to broaden its appeal further. The SoDa team will continue offering workshops in thematic areas like geospatial or network analysis, as well as workshops in collaboration with CLARIAH as part of SSHOC-NL initiatives. The task in 2025 will cost **€248,000**, covering coordination and event hosting expenses (€60,000), including the ODISSEI Summer School, preparation of training materials, and related logistical support. The remainder of the costs are associated with educational coordination and are split between the ODISSEI and CLARIAH coordination teams.

The program provided an excellent opportunity to learn about innovative topics in computational social sciences, such as machine learning and network analysis while connecting with a diverse group of fellow junior social scientists. The combination of practical workshops, guest presentations from prominent scholars, and social activities made for an enjoyable experience.

Henry Abbink, Maastricht School of Business and Economics

4.3. SUPPORT

The Support task bridges the gap between social scientists and infrastructure by providing active support in the use of the ODISSEI's data and analytical infrastructure.

Task leader

Daniel Oberski (d.Loberski@uu.nl)

In ODISSEI, research support is delivered directly through access to technical and methodological expertise within the Social Data Science (SoDa) team, Research Software Engineers (RSE) of the eScience Center and FAIR Expertise Hub for the Social Sciences. Each team offers different types of support.

The SoDa team engages in short-term collaborative projects with social scientists across ODISSEI member organisations, to address innovative research questions and provide support with other infrastructure components, including OSSC, Microdata, eScience, and LISS panel. The team also offers a fellowship program starting from September 2023. The program seeks to provide early career researchers with paid opportunities to develop skills under the supervision of team members and spread this expertise in the ODISSEI community. During the appointment as a SoDa fellow, scientists spend 3-5 months working on data-related projects in social sciences.

During this time, they are paid members of the SoDa team at the Methodology & Statistics department of Utrecht University, mentored by one of the senior team members. Upon completion of their fellowship, each SoDa fellow shares their expertise with the ODISSEI community, for example through a tutorial on a specific method, a lecture, etc., but also through supporting peers in the home organization. The programme has been gaining a lot of interest from the community and so far, three fellowships have been awarded.

The eScience Center team supports projects that align with the ODISSEI strategic goals, with a strong emphasis on projects using the administrative data to be executed in the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC). At the same time, the FAIR Expertise Hub assists researchers and data providers in applying the FAIR principles and documenting their efforts via FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs).

The ODISSEI FAIR support desk publishes blog posts explaining FAIR-related concepts for social scientists and holds a weekly Q&A (hosted by DANS) on FAIR and RDM; in 2024, research on the choice of access restrictions to data and motivations behind them was conducted.

SoDa team executes 7 projects per year on average with room for new projects during 2025 in conjunction with CLARIAH in SSHOC-NL (€186k). NLeSC provides further and more intensive support to several projects, focusing on the expansion of the network file of the whole Dutch population or supporting the execution of machine learning applications in predicting life outcomes.

The support activities by FAIR Expertise Hub are financed via PDI-SSH and TDCC (€199,000). It is expected that this work will then receive structural support through PDI-SSH. The budget for all support tasks in 2025 will be **€540,000** with €65,000 of this allocated for CLARIAH support via SSHOC-NL.

SoDa fellowship project

Using text analysis to build a Dutch historical disease database based on newspaper sources

An important factor in studying an infectious disease involves the timing of exposure. Yet, for the nineteenth- and early twentieth-century Netherlands, such an indicator of the disease environment (timing and place of the outbreak) is lacking. Instead, mortality rates are used as proxies. This fellowship will focus on creating a comprehensive dataset of disease mentions based on historical newspapers (published from 1811 to 1940) in an attempt to overcome data scarcity in this field of study. With the support of the SoDa team, the fellow will tackle methodological issues related to creating such a database- excluding 'false positives' and an issue of representativeness. The outputs of this project will be open-source software and a historical disease database. These outputs will be valuable for researchers from a number of different disciplines, including epidemiology, history, economics and demography. International researchers can use and/or adapt the software to create similar databases in other countries and languages.

Kristina Thompson, Wageningen University & Research

FINANCIAL PLAN 2025

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FINANCIAL PLAN 2025

Table 1 below represents the planned expenditures for 2025 and includes multiple projects in which ODISSEI will be engaged through this period. Because ODISSEI is an infrastructure and not a collection of unrelated projects, the project budgets are collated in a single programme of work alongside membership contributions. The budgets are then delineated by task. These are the tasks that structure section 3 of the annual plan. The tasks in each project are closely monitored on an annual basis by the ODISSEI Management Board and their budgets are then adjusted to optimise the tasks' development and deliverables for the ODISSEI community.

The membership contributions are included in what is referred to as the 'Core Budget'. For 2025, we have budgeted for membership revenue of €530,000. It is expected that revenues will be higher than this as the average 2020-24 is €730,000. We take a conservative estimation for two reasons. First, fiscal uncertainty in the University sector warrants caution both in terms of revenue projections but also expenditure requirements. Second, at the time of writing there was no confirmation of PDI-SSH structural funding. If confirmed, this would extend the operational budget by €1.4 million and add several new services to ODISSEI. If not confirmed, the financial requirements to sustain core ODISSEI services would be significantly affected.

Given this, a budgetary amendment will be submitted to the Supervisory Board in Spring 2025 that incorporates the imminent decision on PDI-SSH and the realized membership contributions. The budget presented in table 1 ensures that the ODISSEI infrastructure can continue to offer existing services to member organizations through 2025. The Spring amendment budget will then reflect how these services can be reenforced or extended given the evolving climate.

The task marked 'CLARIAH' represents activities within SSHOC-NL which are dominated by CLARIAH and whose ODISSEI involvement is limited. The majority of tasks in SSHOC-NL are collaborative but a small number concentrate on key investments in the respective ODISSEI and CLARIAH communities. In SSHOC-NL, tasks 2.3 and 3.1 represent these CLARIAH specific tasks.

Table 1 – Budgeted Revenue & Expenditure for 2025 (2024 included as reference)

ODISSEI Tasks	Revenue 2025			Expenditure	
	Core (k€)	SSHOC-NL (k€)	Other (k€)	2024 (k€)	2025 (k€)
CBS	95	296		480	391
Portal		465		771	465
OSSC	220			342	220
SANE		405	17	743	422
Data Collection		274		715	274
LISS panel	95	250		620	345
MCAL				88	0
PORT		191		20	191
Mass Online Experiments		230		122	230
Disclosure Risk in Networks		173		208	173
Coordination		406	20	736	426
Education	60	188		214	248
Support	90	251	199	859	540
CLARIAH in SSHOC-NL		575		267	575
Total	560	3,703	236	6,184	4,499

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

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KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

ODISSEI maintains a register of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that were initiated at the beginning of the current Roadmap period. Each year, the current status of each KPI is reported and new targets are established. The KPIs are proposed by the Coordination Team and Management Board and amended and approved by the ODISSEI Supervisory Board to ensure continuity and alignment with regard to the specific and concrete aims of the project. In 2025, ODISSEI will enter a new post roadmap phase of development and it is therefore necessary to update and extend the KPIs. To this end, two sets of KPIs are presented. Table 2 provides the KPIs for the Roadmap Period with those KPIs that were realized marked in Green. Table 3 provides the KPIs for the period 2025-2029 and for which many items do not yet have established measures or targets.

Table 2 – Key Performance Indicators 2020-2024

Indicator	Target	Current
Development		
Participation of all social science and economics faculties	All social science and 9 economics faculties to be full ODISSEI members by 2025	All social science faculties and 11 Economics faculties are members.
Participation in European projects	Active participation in at least two European Level projects by 2025	ODISSEI is now a partner in SoBigData Europe and TWIN4DEM, collaborates with EOSC-ENTRUST.
International infrastructure collaborations	Formal collaboration with similar initiatives in UK, US, FR, and DE by 2024	ODISSEI White Paper has been published and ODISSEI is host of IPDLN for 2025-26
Data Access & Analysis		
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations submitting a proposal	Receive project proposals from 10% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations	Currently approximately 11% of all researchers have submitted
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project	Provide access to 5% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations by 2025	Currently 3% of all researchers have received a grant
Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal	50 unique visitors per month by 2025	41 unique visitors per month
Number of OSSC Projects per year	7 per year for 2022, 2023 and 2024	17 active in 2024
Number of projects spanning more than 2 service providers	5 per year by 2025	19 projects in 2024
Financial		
Further successful funding applications	Participation in a successful 2022 Roadmap Application for SSH	SSHOC-NL awarded and Macroscope under consideration
Total amount committed by member organisations	By 2025, to receive continuation of existing commitments to 2029 as a minimum	80% of partners have committed until 2031 conditional on Macroscope award

Training & Education		
Number of attendees at training events and workshops	600 unique attendees at events per year	1015 for 2024
Number of projects supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)	15 projects completed before end of 2024	28 projects acquired up to October 2024
Science & Technology		
Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure	3 per year by 2025	5 in 2024
Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	30 per year by 2025	44 in 2023-24 (until October)
Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	200 per year by 2025	304 in 2024 (until October)
Social and Economic Impact		
Number of datasets contributed by non-academic organisations	Five datasets from non-academic organisations accessible by 2025	10
Number of government agencies participating as member organisations	7 by 2025	6
Number of website visits	50,000 per year by 2025	80,000 in 2024
Mentions in key policy documents	3 per year	5 in 2024
Communication		
Number of social media (e.g. X(Twitter), LinkedIn) subscribers	2,500 by 2025	2,559
Number of newsletter subscribers	Total of 1,000 by 2025	1,434
Attracting New Talent		
Number of international scientists using ODISSEI	20 by the end of 2024	18
Number of major grants using ODISSEI (e.g. NWO talent, MCSA, ERC etc)	5 per year	9 in 2024

Key Performance Indicators 2025-2029

The ODISSEI Management Board has indicated a need to update and revise the Key Performance Indicators for the period 2025-2029. During this period, there must be a shift in focus from creating the infrastructure and community that surround it towards providing a mature, usable and scalable infrastructure that is increasingly accessible and supportive of ground breaking science. These KPIs are directed toward a core underlying mission for the period.

By 2029, the experience of researchers at ODISSEI member organizations should be that *'it just works'*. Currently, the infrastructure consists of services in development or that require persistence, patience, and perseverance in usage. The coming years will focus on ever simplifying user workflows and eradicating points of friction. The KPIs are directed towards this simple goal. In the forthcoming 12 months, the focus will be on further expanding the reach and scope of ODISSEI and ensuring that its membership organizations receive an improving return on investment.

Table 3 – Key Performance Indicators 2025-2029

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Target</i>	<i>Current</i>
Development		
Participation of all social science and economics faculties	All social science and economics faculties as members	All but 3 Economics Faculties
Participation in European projects	Direct participation in at least five European Level projects by 2029	Direct participation in SoBigData Europe
International infrastructure collaborations	Formal participation in European or Global RI	None
Data Access & Analysis		
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations submitting a proposal	Receive project proposals from 30% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations	11%
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project	Provide access to 25% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations by 2029	3%
Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal	500 unique visitors per month by 2029	41
Number of OSSC Projects per year	30 Active Projects by 2029	16 Active Projects
Number of projects spanning more than 2 service providers	50 per year by 2029	19
Financial		
Diversification of financing	Funding from 3 different funding bodies representing more than 5% of annual expenditure	1 (NWO)
Financial Stability	100% of operational costs covered by structural financing	62%
Training & Education		
Number of attendees at training events and workshops	2,000 unique attendees at events per year	1015
Number of projects supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)	100 projects completed before end of 2029	28

Science		
Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure	10 per year by 2029	5 in 2024
Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	30 per year by 2029	44 in 2023-24 (until October)
Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	200 per year by 2029	304 in 2024 (until October)
Technical		
Service Outages	Number of service outages per year	TBD
DAB Request Response time	Average time in hours until access granted	TBD
Scalability of SANE	Number of concurrent users supported	TBD
Error Rate	Rate of errors reported per user per month	TBD
Social & Economic Impact		
Recognition as Infrastructure under Data Governance Act	TBD	TBD
Return on Investment of ODISSEI	TBD	TBD
Number of website visits	1,000,000 per year by 2029	80,000 in 2024
Mentions in key policy documents	10 per year	5 in 2024
Communication		
Number of social media (e.g. X(Twitter), LinkedIn) subscribers	25,000 by 2029	2,559
Number of newsletter subscribers	Total of 5,000 by 2029	1,434
Attracting & Retaining Talent		
Number of international scientists using ODISSEI	50 by the end of 2029	18
Number of major grants using ODISSEI (e.g. NWO talent, MCSA, ERC etc)	20 per year	9 in 2024
Retention of Coordination Staff	80% retention year on year	100%
Sustainability & Environmental		
Carbon Footprint of HPC Usage	Reporting of annual carbon footprint based on SSH HPC usage at SURF	TBD

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